

TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNGSTERS THROUGH PICTURES

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Abstract: This article is written on the methods of teaching English to youngsters, and at the moment English is the world language, developing day by day. For this reason, English should be started with children from kindergarten age, and this article will tell you about it.

Аннотация: В этой статье описаны методы обучения английскому языку маленьких детей, и в настоящее время английский язык становится языком мира с каждым днем. По этой причине английский язык следует начинать с детского сада, и эта статья расскажет вам об этом.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola yoshlarga ingliz tilini o'rgatish usullari yozilgan bo'lib, hozirgi vaqtda ingliz tili dunyo tili bo'lib kundun kunga rivojlanib bormoqda. Shu sababli, ingliz tilini bolalarga bog'cha yoshidan boshlash kerak va bu maqola shu haqida ma'lumot beradi.

Key words: foreign language, words, phonetics, rule, methodology, rhythmic music games

INTRODUCTION: In the last few years, learning a foreign language has become a necessity, not a way of self-development. Foreign language has become a mandatory component of education not only in schools and universities, but also in many additional pre-school institutions.

The demand for foreign languages in our country, especially today, the demand for English, is increasing day by day. Moreover, the understanding by parents that language is not only a factor in the upbringing of a modern person, but also the basis of his social and material well-being in society, on the other hand means that this moment should make the early learning of a foreign language relevant. 20 years ago, language proficiency was required only in the work of some areas, while nowadays, knowledge of at least 2 languages (English, Russian) creates a lot.

The main problem of teaching a foreign language is the student's age. Until recently, the teaching methodology was aimed at the school age of children, now parents are trying to start teaching a foreign language as early as possible. The main goals of teaching preschool children to a foreign language:

* formation of initial communication skills in a foreign language in children;

- ability to achieve their goals, use a foreign language to express thoughts and feelings in the context of life communication;
- * create a positive attitude towards further study of foreign languages;
- * to arouse interest in the life and culture of other countries.

Preschool age is especially convenient for starting to learn a foreign language. Children of this age are characterized by their sensitivity to language phenomena, they are interested in understanding their speech experience, the "secrets" of the language.

There is another reason why early age is preferable for learning a foreign language. The younger the child, the less. Vocabulary in local language, but at the same time it also has few needs for speech: in a small child, communication areas are less than in adults, it does not yet have to solve complex communication problems. This means that when she masters a foreign language, she does not notice such a big difference between opportunities in mother and foreign languages, and her sense of success becomes brighter than that of older children. Teaching children is a rather difficult issue that requires a completely different methodological approach than schoolchildren and adults. If an adult speaks a foreign language, this does not mean that he can teach others. Faced with stylistically disadvantaged classes, children can hate a foreign language for a long time and lose confidence in their abilities. Only experienced professionals should work with preschool children.

In preschool age, when teaching English, children gradually develop the basics of communicative competence, which includes the following aspects at the initial stage of learning English:

- ability to reproduce correctly from a phonetic point of view English words behind a teacher, native speaker or speaker, that is, the gradual formation of auditory attention, phonetic hearing and correct pronunciation;
- mastering, combining and activating English Vocabulary;
- * mastering a certain number of simple grammatical structures, drawing up a coherent statement.

The methodology should be built taking into account the age and individual characteristics of the structure of children's language skills, conducting direct educational activities, and be aimed at their development. Communication in a foreign language should be motivational and directed. It is necessary to create a positive psychological attitude towards a foreign language in a child, and the way to create such a positive motivation is to play. The game is both a form of organization and a way of conducting classes in which children accumulate a

certain amount of English vocabulary, learn a lot of poems, songs, counting rhymes, etc.

This form of conducting classes creates favorable conditions for mastering language skills and speech skills. The ability to believe in game activity allows you to give a natural impetus to speech in a foreign language, to make even the simplest phrases interesting and meaningful. Playing a foreign language in teaching is not contrary to educational activities, but organically related to it.

Rhythmic music games are any traditional games, such as Dances with a choice of partners, which help not to master communication skills, but to improve the phonetic and ritmomelodic aspects of speech and immerse yourself in the spirit of language, for example: "nuts and may ", "What Are you? name ", " I like my friends", "heard, shoulders, knees and toes", etc.

Artistic or creative games. It is a type of activity that stands at the limit of play and artistic creation, and the path to it corresponds to the child through play. They, in turn, can be divided.

The peculiarity of teaching English to preschoolers is that he simply sits at a table and does not leaf through books and notebooks. The process should not be boring, and children themselves should strive for knowledge. Children think clearly, take everything literally, speak simple sentences... if the teacher explains something, he should give clarity, an example. Therefore, English is a game for preschool children. Only through this form can you achieve positive results and form a positive attitude towards a foreign language in a child.

Forms of education should be able not to master as many lexical units as possible, but to educate interest in the topic, develop the child's communication skills and express their thoughts. In the competence of the child, it is important to achieve certain qualities of mastering the material, allowing to provide the child with a minimum of funds, which will take over the further growth of language units, their situational and meaningful use.

From the very beginning of training, it is necessary to develop a certain style of working with children in English, to introduce rituals that correspond to the most typical situations of communication. Such rituals (greeting, farewell, short exercises, the use of tactful formulas adopted in English) allow children to establish a foreign language connection, facilitate the transition to English, show children that the lesson has begun, now a certain stage of the lesson is going on.

Primary school students in rural areas usually grow up in conditions that are far from the English language environment, and children's thinking remains in an abstract form, while the process of children's assimilation of new knowledge is

always carried out with a reliance on emotions. Therefore, English teachers for kindergarten-age children use the items, cards, and other teaching aids around students to the fullest through easy teaching methodologies. When teaching words such as "Banana" and "apple", teachers can also teach new words denoting color at once, showing fruits such as bananas and apples. Children are taught to use them in a foreign language through objects in the classroom to organize training sessions.

Definitely, when using items during training, the teachers' methodology plays a big role. For example, when teaching the appropriate words, you are encouraged to speak it by showing the item to the child first, the students pronounce the words and, to reinforce the word they pronounce, they are once again pronounced the new word again using the pictures on the cards. When teaching words, teachers will be able to define the content of the text and, in order to attract the attention of students, the educator will be able to attract their attention by using them to pronounce the words and draw a picture on the board.

Therefore, now in China, a tutor is required to have the skill of drawing. This not only shortens the difficulties of teaching, but also helps students gradually consolidate the knowledge learned. In order for students to feel the progress they have in learning English, it is necessary to approach each study session perfectly. Only then does the motivation for learning awaken in children. Currently, the teaching programs in kindergartens have been intensified accordingly, as the opportunities for Chinese kindergarten-age children to receive new knowledge have become very advanced.

The use of song and action games to improve the classroom environment.

Creating a flexible class atmosphere is sometimes more important than any educational method. At the beginning of the lesson in the classroom, all the children, led by a teacher with a pleasant English song, sang together and danced a little to suit her tone. It helps to become even more refreshed and memorize the words of the song faster, while purring their bodies from themselves. The English environment, importantly, allows you to naturally enter a good learning atmosphere.

Cartoons. Although children do not understand the statements in the cartoon during learning a foreign language, they try to understand the words they are using through the actions of the characters in the cartoon. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn a language.

Currently, all kindergartens in China are equipped with multimedia devices. For children, English is taught from songs to poems and stories, through videos. This makes zercillary language lessons a fun day game. In Chinese kindergartens, there are about 10 foster children in one Gruh, and the caregiver regularly applies the method of upbringing to each child based on his pisichology. This requires the educator not only to remain a tutor, but also to be an artist, musician, foreign language reader, and a good psychologist mother at the same time.

CONCLUSION: In conclusion, teaching through Multimedia gives the educator great opportunities. In doing so, it is possible to raise the interest of bollards to a high level and keep their attention focused for a long time. Through this, we can see that the skills of the child in the language have increased.

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